

SOUND INSULATION PROPERTIES OF TIMBER FRAME: SIMULATION AND COMPARISON OF RESULTS

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In literature, there is an extensive treatment of material characterization in the acoustic field for timber frame and new sustainable materials for insulation. From this, it is possible to identify ranges for each parameter useful for simulation. Indeed, many authors rely on either data from previous works or data obtained from laboratory tests. However, the intervals of values for the parameters in the acoustic field is quite wide. The ranges identified by a literature study will be simulated for the same timber construction element under the same conditions. Then, by varying each parameter within the corresponding range, the results will be compared to understand how the variation of material characterization affects the simulation phase and the final results.

Keywords: timber frame, simulation, sound insulation, material characterization

1. Introduction

The eco-sustainability qualities of timber buildings and of their construction processes are well acknowledged [1], [2], [3]. Timber is one of the most eco-friendly raw resource, suitable for construction and characterized mainly by (i) wide availability in nature and (ii) relative ease of handling [4]. It is a pioneering material thanks to environmental friendliness and with a broad scope of end-reuses. At present, a large number of studies has been focused on wood properties for construction purpose and various types of building solutions were engineered [5].

Particularly, in acoustic field simulation has a major role to optimize the design phase and the insulation material choice [6]. Indeed, sound insulation design is a complex process in interior design [7] and in building acoustics design [8], [9]. In this framework, one of the main timber components simulated and adopted for its customizable sound insulation performance is timber frame [10]. Indeed, the wide adoption of timber frame among timber building construction components is related to its performance on thermal [11], structural [12] and acoustic [13] behaviour.

In order to investigate the availability of scientific material regarding this structural component that is highly popular among designers and in research, a bibliographic research on its acoustic performance and the parameters that characterize it was carried out. Therefore, a simulation process followed to highlight the disparity of the timber frame characterizing parameters available on the several scientific databases and its influence on the simulation of the timber frame acoustic performance. Consequently, an analysis and a comparison of the results was carried out.

2. Identification and research of useful data for the simulation phase.

To research and collect useful data for the simulation phase a bibliographic research was conducted on two main databases: Google Scholar and Scopus. In this databases mechanical and acoustic parameters characterization were researched in order to fulfil the input data for the simulation phase required by the simulation software.

Particularly, the parameters required for the Transfer Matrix Method used in the simulation phase were investigated. Then, for the acoustical characterization the research focused on the airborne transmission in a frequency domain investigation. In this case the parameters were detected basing on the Johnson et al. [14] approach, modified by Champoux and Allard [15], is most of the time used to model the five factors influencing this phenomenon, namely:

- flow resistivity $\sigma \left[\frac{Ns}{m^4} \right]$,
- porosity $\phi [-]$,
- tortuosity $\alpha_{\infty} [-]$,
- viscous characteristic length $\Lambda [\mu m]$
- thermal characteristic length $\Lambda' [\mu m]$.

For the solid-borne sound propagation, the Hook's law relates a proportional dependence between stresses and strains. For isotropic elastic solids, it can be written in matrix form as (Eq. (1)):

$$(1) \quad \sigma = C\varepsilon$$

where σ is the stress tensor applied to the elastic isotropic mean and ε is the obtained strain tensor. C is defined as function of the Young's Modulus (E) and the Poisson's ratio (ν) [16]. Thus, for the characterisation of the mechanical behaviour of materials, for the purposes of the TMM, it was necessary to seek values for the mechanical characterisation with regard to:

- Bulk density, ρ
- Young's modulus, E
- Poisson's ratio, ν .

With the aim to obtain the above-mentioned parameters between the two main databases chose, two main research were conducted in each database searching for those parameters needed for the input phase of the simulation.

A first general research was mainly conducted to find the mechanical parameters characterizing each layer of the Timber Frame or giving ranges for a general Timber Frame structure. This was performed using simply the keywords "material characterization" in combination or with (i) "timber stud"; (ii) "insulation material"; (iii) "oriented strand board" or "OSB".

The second research, among the results found, focused on the combination of keywords summarized in Table 1. As highlighted by this table, the combination of keywords can be classified in two main categories, each distinguished by whether it belongs to the "performance" or "simulation" macro area.

Table 1: summary of keywords adopted for the bibliographic research aimed to data collection

Performance	Simulation
"Timber Frame" AND "performance"	"Timber Frame" AND "simulation"
"Timber Frame" AND "acoustic insulation" AND "performance"	"Timber Frame" AND "acoustic insulation" AND "simulation"
"Timber Frame" AND "sound insulation" AND "performance"	"Timber Frame" AND "sound insulation" AND "simulation"
"Timber Frame" AND "noise insulation" AND "performance"	"Timber Frame" AND "noise insulation" AND "simulation"

Title, results and data reported have been examined for each work found with the combination of keywords method presented above. With this procedure was possible to acquire the information potentially relevant for the aim of this study and the outcomes of this screening process were taken into account in the data archive.

After this process, the literature, considered pertinent and providing the physical values researched, has been listed and indexed. Consequently, only those data have been considered for the simulation phase. Conversely, excluding criteria were adopted, to better focus on the topics investigated in this work. The criteria excluding papers are:

- the characterization of materials used in building elements other than Timber Frame;
- the characterization of a physical parameter not included in the list defined in **Error! Reference source not found.**

No excluding criteria have been adopted related to the year of publishing.

3. Results of bibliographic research and data collection

Timber Frame is a multilayer building component that is mainly composed by a timber stud, an oriented strand board (OSB) and an insulation layer. In the following section results of the research will be depicted for each composing element of the Timber Frame, analysing the results for sake of brevity only for minimum and maximum values, while in the tables each value and the correspondent author is indicated.

3.1 . Timber stud.

The results of the timber stud parameters characterization are depicted in Table 2. For each data acquired, the corresponding author is indicated. Then, also if several results were detected for the mechanical parameters, study on acoustic parameters characterization of timber stud are missing.

Table 2: summary of the literature research for the characterization of timber stud

Timber Stud								
source	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	ϕ [%]	σ [kPa s/m ²]	α_{∞} [μm]	Λ [μm]	Λ' [μm]
[17]	-	8960-19240	-	-	-	-	-	-
[18]	532							
[19]	455							
[20]	340	10000						
[21]	455							
[22]	400-700							

3.2 . Oriented Strand Board (OSB)

Only few authors listed parameters for OSB As for the case of timber stud, no acoustical characterization reporting the researched parameters synthesized in **Error! Reference source not found.** was found among literature investigated. A synthetic summary about the OSB physical characterization can be seen in Table 3 in which are then also indicated the value identified and the corresponding authors who characterised, reported or indicated them.

Table 3: summary of the literature research for the characterization of OSB

Oriented Strand Board								
source	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	ϕ [%]	σ [kPa s/m ²]	α_{∞} [μm]	Λ [μm]	Λ' [μm]
[17]	-	4410-6280	-	-	-	-	-	-
[18]	646							
[19]	595							

[20]	550	3800						
[21]	615							
[23]	700	3800	0,2					
[24]	600							

3.3 Insulation: Rock wool

A synthetic summary about the rock wool physical characterization is reported in Table 4. For each data acquired, the corresponding author is indicated. Conversely to the timber stud and the OSB, rock-wool parameters characterization foreseen also acoustical characterization.

Table 4: summary of the literature research for the characterization of rock wool

Rock wool								
source	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	ϕ [%]	σ [kPa s/m ²]	α_{∞} [μ m]	Λ [μ m]	Λ' [μ m]
[23]	40	-	-	0.98	15.4	1.04	56	
[25]	44	0.014	0	0.99	14.08	1	137	76
[26]	70							11
[27]	21			0.98	15.5	1.1		
[28]	183			0.97	51.2	1.06	41	

4. Simulation with the obtained input data

Thanks to the extensive data provided by the previous literature search, it was possible to carry out numerous simulations by varying the input data and studying their influence on the final result. The following is an analysis of the data by varying the parameters concerned for each element constituting the timber frame. The simulations were performed studying the variation of the sound insulation index (R_w) with the variation of the parameters listed in the previous sections. For the simulation a simple timber wall was performed, as depicted in Figure 1.

For sake of brevity, for each composing element of the timber frame was performed a variation of the input data parameters except for the insulation material where two input variations were studied for completeness.

Figure 1: Model structure of the partition used for simulation purposes

4.1 Timber stud results.

Due to the results of the literature research of timber stud depicted in Table 2, the variation performed was on a mechanical parameter. Particularly, this simulation focused on varying the Young's modulus of elasticity (E).

It can be seen from Figure 2 that as the elastic modulus varies, the soundproofing behaviour of the wall varies as well. Indeed, by gradually increasing only the timber stud elasticity modulus among the

input data, it is highlighted how as the elasticity of the stud used increases (darker tonality of blue), the sound insulation index of the entire timber frame wall decreases.

Figure 2: Influence of only the elasticity modulus of stud on the sound insulation index of the entire Timber Frame building partition

4.2 Oriented Strand Board results.

As for the case of timber stud, for the OSB the only provided input data from literature research, detailed in Table 2, were the mechanical parameters. Consequently, the variation parameters chosen for OSB to be varied in this case was the density.

By analysing the results in Figure 3 it can be seen how the density strongly influence the sound index insulation of the timber frame wall. Indeed, it can be seen how increasing the density of the only OSB, the sound insulation index increases and the whole timber frame partition benefits from the increased insulation.

Figure 3: Influence of only the density of OSB on the sound insulation index of the entire Timber Frame building partition

4.3 Rock wool results.

Conversely to the other components of timber wall, for the insulation layer, particularly in case of the rock-wool, data inputs were available both for the mechanical and for the acoustic characterization of the material, as depicted in Table 4.

The results in Figure 4 show the variation of the sound insulation index of the timber frame partition by varying the air flow resistivity of only the insulation layer. From that, it is highlighted how the by varying one of the acoustical parameters, the impact on the variation of sound insulation performance induced is negligible.

Figure 4: Influence of only the flow resistivity of rock wool on the sound insulation index of the entire Timber Frame building partition

To better understand the influence of the material characterization of the insulation layer on the sound insulation performance of the timber wall, also a mechanical data input variation was performed for thoroughness. From the analysis proposed in Figure 5 it can be appreciated that even in the case of significant variations in the density of the insulating material within the timber frame structure, the influence on the sound insulation provided by the entire wall is minimal.

Figure 5: Influence of only the density of rock wool on the sound insulation index of the entire Timber Frame building partition

5. Discussion and Conclusion

From what has been analysed so far, two fundamental points have emerged.

Firstly, from the analysis of the literature performed it can be seen that there are numerous papers characterising the different materials constituting the timber frame, but only a few characterise the materials acoustically and many, especially in the cases of timber stud and OSB, only characterise the materials mechanically.

Secondly, the availability of these values in the various studies identified significantly influences the information that will be gathered by the reader. Particularly, if one wanted to use the data obtained from the analysis to simulate the behaviour of a timber frame wall, the simulation results could be highly influenced by the source of the input data. Particularly, it was found that by varying only one parameter of a single material at a time, only the characteristics of the timber materials influence the acoustic performance in the soundproofing of a timber frame wall.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Zhen, B. Zhang, Energy Performance of a Light Wood-Timber Structured House in the Severely Cold Region of China, *Sustainability*. 10 (2018) 1501. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10051501>.
- [2] A. Stocchero, J.K. Seadon, R. Falshaw, M. Edwards, Urban Equilibrium for sustainable cities and the contribution of timber buildings to balance urban carbon emissions: A New Zealand case study, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 143 (2017) 1001–1010.
- [3] J. Tollefson, The wooden skyscrapers that could help to cool the planet, *Nature News*. 545 (2017) 280.
- [4] M. Ramage, H. Burrige, M. Wicher, G. Fereday, T. Reynolds, D. Shah, G. Wu, L. Yu, P. Fleming, D. Densley Tingley, J. Allwood, P. Dupree, P.F. Linden, O. Scherman, The wood from the trees: The use of timber in construction, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 68 (2017) 333–359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.09.107>.
- [5] M.K. Kuzman, D. Sandberg, Comparison of timber-house technologies and initiatives supporting use of timber in Slovenia and in Sweden - the state of the art, *IForest - Biogeosciences and Forestry*. (2017) 930–938. <https://doi.org/10.3832/ifor2397-010>.
- [6] S. Pelzer, L. Aspöck, D. Schröder, M. Vorländer, Integrating real-time room acoustics simulation into a cad modeling software to enhance the architectural design process, *Buildings*. 4 (2014) 113–138.
- [7] W. Lin, H. Lin, Z.Y. Huang, Y.H. Lee, Concerning the Perspective of Sound Insulation on Approaches of Interior Design, in: *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*, Springer, 2020: pp. 516–525.
- [8] W.N. Hien, L.K. Poh, H. Feriadi, The use of performance-based simulation tools for building design and evaluation—a Singapore perspective, *Building and Environment*. 35 (2000) 709–736.
- [9] C.M. Mak, Z. Wang, Recent advances in building acoustics: An overview of prediction methods and their applications, *Building and Environment*. 91 (2015) 118–126.
- [10] H.A. Metzen, R. Schumacher, Prediction of sound insulation in timber frame buildings, in: *Proceedings of Forum Acusticum, Budimpešta, Mađarska*, 2005: pp. 2347–2352.
- [11] H. Fu, Y. Ding, M. Li, Y. Cao, W. Xie, Z. Wang, Research and simulation analysis of thermal performance and hygrothermal behavior of timber-framed walls with different external thermal insulation layer: Cork board and anticorrosive pine plate, *Journal of Building Physics*. (2020) 1744259120936720.
- [12] X. Li, J. Zhao, G. Ma, W. Chen, Experimental study on the seismic performance of a double-span traditional timber frame, *Engineering Structures*. 98 (2015) 141–150.
- [13] B. Nusser, C. Lux, External timber frame walls-Effects of façade type, internal linings and construction details on measured sound insulation, in: *INTER-NOISE and NOISE-CON Congress and Conference Proceedings*, Institute of Noise Control Engineering, 2020: pp. 1394–1399.
- [14] D.L. Johnson, J. Koplik, R. Dashen, Theory of dynamic permeability and tortuosity in fluid-saturated porous media, *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*. 176 (1987) 379–402. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112087000727>.
- [15] Y. Champoux, J. Allard, Dynamic tortuosity and bulk modulus in air-saturated porous media, *Journal of Applied Physics*. 70 (1991) 1975–1979. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.349482>.
- [16] J. Allard, N. Atalla, *Propagation of sound in porous media: modelling sound absorbing materials 2e*, John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [17] Z. Cai, R.J. Ross, Mechanical Properties of Wood-Based Composite Materials, in: *Wood Handbook : Wood as an Engineering Material: Chapter 12, Madison, WI : U.S. Dept. of Agriculture, Forest Service, Forest Products Laboratory*, 2010: p. 12.1-12.12.
- [18] P. Pihelo, T. Kalamees, The effect of thermal transmittance of building envelope and material selection of wind barrier on moisture safety of timber frame exterior wall, *Journal of Building Engineering*. 6 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobee.2016.02.002>.
- [19] C. Coupillie, M. Steemana, N. Van Den Bosschea, K. Maroy, Evaluating the hygrothermal performance of prefabricated timber frame façade elements used in building renovation, in: *Elsevier Ltd., Trondheim, Norway*, 2017: pp. 933–938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.09.727>.
- [20] K. Villa, C. Echavarría, D. Blessent, Wood walls insulated with coconut fiber, *Revista DYNA*. 86 (2019) 333–337. <https://doi.org/10.15446/dyna.v86n210.73685>.
- [21] S.J. Chang, S. Wi, S. Kim, Thermal bridging analysis of connections in cross-laminated timber buildings based on ISO 10211, *Construction and Building Materials*. 213 (2019) 709–722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.04.009>.
- [22] H.M. Kunzel, *Simultaneous Heat and Moisture Transport in Building Components: one and two dimensional calculation using simple parameters.*, 1995.
- [23] M. Caniato, P. Bonfiglio, F. Bettarello, A. Gasparella, Innovative Approach in Acoustic Simulation of Timber Walls, in: *16th IBPSA International Conference and Exhibition, Rome*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.26868/25222708.2019.211114>.
- [24] B. Ingelaere, CHAPTER 4 ACOUSTIC DESIGN OF LIGHTWEIGHT TIMBER FRAME CONSTRUCTIONS, in: *Action FP0702: Forests, Their Products and Services*, n.d.
- [25] M. Caniato, F. Bettarello, P. Bonfiglio, A. Gasparella, Extensive investigation of multiphysics approaches in simulation of complex periodic structures, *Applied Acoustics*. 166 (2020) 107356.
- [26] X. Zhu, B.-J. Kim, Q. Wang, Q. Wu, Recent Advances in the Sound Insulation Properties of Bio-based materials, *BioResources*. 9 (2013) 1764–1786.
- [27] N. Dauchez, M. Etchessahar, S. Sahraoui, On measurement of mechanical properties of sound absorbing materials, in: 2002.

- [28] X. Olny, R. Panneton, Acoustical determination of the parameters governing thermal dissipation in porous media, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 123 (2008) 814–824. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2828066>.